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LETTER OF PUBLICATION

To, Authors,

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Greetings!

As our peer editorial review process, It's a great pleasure to inform you that, Your Manuscript Entitle, "**The Maliki Doctrine in Andalusia: From the Scientific Voyage to the Official Authority of the Umayyad State A Socio-Historical Study on the Causes of Spread and Factors of Empowerment**" has been accepted and considered for Publication in our **TECHNICAL COMMUNICATION** in Volume No. 25– issue 1-(2025).

Thank you for submitting your work to this journal.

Best Regards,

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